

Temple of Jayanti Devi: A Study

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Abstract

Jayanti Devi is approximately a six hundred-year-old temple situated in Majri village, Punjab. This temple is dedicated to a goddess. The temple structure looks like a fort and lies on the top of a mountain. The villagers are engaged in the maintenance of the temple. The area around the temple requires development. The promotion of tourism in the area can benefit the local population and the temple. It can generate a source of income and employment for the villagers. Through various activities, the social and economic conditions of the village can be improved.

Key Words: Religious structure, tourism, employment generation activities.

Introduction

Temples in India have played a significant role in social and cultural life. It gave rise to the traditions, values, and norms in society. As we all know India is the land of sacred places, which have existed since ancient times. Religious structures like votive tanks, and figurines of mother goddesses and seals have been found in Harappan cities. Throughout the Vedic period, people

worshipped Indra (God of war), Agni (fire goddess), Uma, Varuna, and many other deities. They performed different rituals although no permanent structures as temples have yet been found to belong to the Vedic period. Possibly the structures were made out of perishable materials like wood, bamboo, and leaves that could not sustain for long. Elaboration of Ritualistic activities and sacrifices led to the augmentation of temple building in ancient India (Gupta S.P and Asthana S.P 2002: 82). The rule of Mauryas in the 3rd BCE led to the formation of caves and stupas for worshipping. The temples built of stone and brick were constructed later and exist today in different parts of our country.

Religious activities are what helped people to interconnect with each other and celebrate festivals together. It gave them a sense of belongingness. It furthermore helped dynasties legitimise their rule as they patronised the temples, craftsmen, and artists. In India, temples are found everywhere. The present paper studies the temple of Jayanti Devi located near Chandigarh.

Fig. 1: Map of Chandigarh

Historical Aspect

Jayanti Devi temple lies in the Majri village also identified as Jayanti Majri. It is located in the Mohali district of Punjab on the bank of the Jayanti River, a seasonal rivulet surrounded by Shivalik hills (Hawley 1998: 250). The temple is fifteen kilometres away from Chandigarh. It is named after the goddess of victory, one of Kangra Valley's seven goddesses. They are also known as the seven sisters, Naina devi, Jwalamukhi, Chintapurni, Mansa, Brajeshwari, Chaamunda, and Jayanti devi situated in Himachal Pradesh (Roy 1998). According to the signboard outside the temple, it is said to be around six hundred years old. An article in Tribune by Amarjit Thind dated it to the time of a Mughal emperor Baber and was constructed by a Rajput king of the eighteenth century who ruled over a state known as Hithnour (Thind 1998). The original temple of the goddess is located in Kangra (Himachal Pradesh). According to the legend, a king reigned over Hithnour situated north of present-day Chandigarh. He got one of his sons wedded to the daughter of the king of Kangra in Himachal Pradesh. The Princess was an ardent devotee of goddess Jayanti Devi since she was a juvenile. Every day she first worshipped the goddess and afterwards participated in other activities. On being betrothed to the king of Hithnour and not being able to endure her separation from the goddess she prayed to the goddess. On seeing the dedication towards her the goddess was mesmerized she decided to appear in her dream and promised that they would not be separated and she will accompany her wherever she goes. After the marriage when the palanquin of the princess was to advance for Hithnour, it became so heavy that it could not be lifted. The princess then reminded her father about her dream, upon hearing the dream king then accepted the desire of his daughter, and another palanquin was arranged for the idol to be placed and sent with the princess to Hithnour. The priest and his family who looked after the goddess also accompanied the goddess to Hithnour (Tomar 2014: 157-159). The idol was later established on the hill that is the present location of this temple. After the demise of the princess, the deity was worshipped for two hundred years by the succeeding generations of the family. Later on, a dacoit called Garibu or Garibdas started terrorizing the region including Mullanpur (presently in Ropar). Progressively Garibu seized the Hithnour estate and started ruling there. However, Garibu looked after the underprivileged and was a great disciple of the goddess Jayanti Devi. According to the Priest, the temple goddess had given a boon to Garibdas that as long as his family name ends with Das, they will keep prospering. The temple was initially small and was later expanded by him and his grandson Bhagwan Das completed the construction of the temple. Every year a fair is organized in the month

of August on the occasion of his birthday in the sanctuary and langar is served to the people (Revenue Department 1987: 450-451).

Fig 2: Jayanti Devi Temple

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Fig. 3: Goddess Jayanti.

Fig. 4: Bhairav devta

The temple has a massive entrance at the base and there is a red flag with red threads and dhvaja tied around it by the devotees. Approximately three hundred and eighty stairs lead to the main shrine built on the summit. On both sides of the temple, there are small shops. Prasad and gifts are sold to the devotees who visit this temple in large numbers. The temple has two langar halls one of them was built during the time of Garibdas and the other one was constructed recently to accommodate the increasing number of devotees. The premises of the temple consist of a water tank, which can be found in most Indian temples, and a lush green forest surrounds this temple. The temple is erected on a 6.10 m high platform and is supported by four octagonal columns measuring 9.8 feet each and walls on all sides. The steps leading up to the shrine get narrower upon reaching the main shrine where the deity is enshrined. The shrine is in the southwest direction, and around the sanctum, there is enough space for circumambulation which measures around 5 feet. The sanctum is square in shape and measures around 9X9 feet hence is a *sandhara* temple. The idol kept inside the sanctum is carved out of stone and has been adorned with beautiful red clothes, gold jewellery, a crown on the head, and a parasol on the top. The panels around the idol have images of Hanuman, Lakshmi, Ram, Sita, and other gods and goddesses carved on them. The entrance of the sanctum is small and only the priest is allowed to enter the sanctum. On the niches outside the wall of the sanctum, there are images of other divinities like Shiva, Ganesha,

Bhairo, Lakshmi, and Kali, and local deities like Lokda deva (Lokda deva is a local folk deity) and Balasundari (Balasundari is a childhood form of goddess Durga). The walls of the temple are covered with ceramic tiles and the floor is clad in white marble. The top of the temple is in the shape of a dome with a red flag on it and is modest in design (Tomar 2016: 1-4).

Fig. 5: Entrance of the temple

Fig. 6: Donations made by the people

On Purnima in the month of February every year, a fair is held at Jayanti Devi and is attended by people from far and wide.

The temple does not get any government assistance and is sustained by two committees that look after the management of the temple. One of them is composed of the priest family, the old Sikh and Hindu residents of Jayanti Majri and the other committee consists of old residents of Mullanpur. The temple receives donations from the devotees who visit it. According to the priest, the donations are used for feeding devotees, ritualistic activities, and yearly maintenance of the temple. The temple immediately needs the government's attention so that the area can develop into a centre of culture. The narrow road which leads to this temple needs to be taken care of as potholes cause inconvenience to the devotees. This site can be developed into a site of tourist importance which would help this village to grow and the youth of the village can be engaged in the sustainable growth of the area. The tourism department can open a small centre/shop to sell handicrafts. Nursery can also come up in the area where the government can sell medicinal plants/flowers by involving the local population. Water sport activities can be organized near Jayanti Dam for the entertainment of tourists. This will generate various employment opportunities for the residents of Jayanti Majri and serve the local population.

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